

Nissen Templum in Cassirer Symbolic Forms

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In the Ernst Cassirer Philosophy of Symbolic Forms, 1925, we can find mentioned some considerations that Heinrich Nissen proposed in his *Das Templum*, 1986. Cassirer is referring to Nissen in the section entitled "Space and Light. The Problem of Orientation". In fact, Cassirer is using the Nissen's belief of *Das Templum* without any critical approach. However, before Cassirer, the Nissen's theory of the roman templum has been criticized by I. M. J. Valeton. In his *De Templis Romanis*, Valeton demonstrated the several pitfalls in Nissen's approach. And Valeton was not the only one that criticized Nissen. Using an expression by Jeremia Pelgrom, 2018, that we can find in his work about the Roman colonial landscape, let us tell that the Nissen's templum belief acceptance by Cassirer was "determined by aprioristic assumptions derived from socio-evolutionary paradigms". We will also stress that the Nissen's belief of the templum arrived almost unrecognized in today archaeoastronomy regarding the roman world.

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Introduction

Heinrich Nissen was a German scholar of philology and ancient history. Among his works we find the *Italischen Landeskunde* (1883, 1902) and the *Das Templum* (1869). Being his work, particularly the *Das Templum*, organized to show the role of orientation in the layout of temples, Nissen is credited being among the first 'archaeoastronomers' in the world (Ruggles, 2005). In his book of 1869, Nissen considered specifically the inaugurated place, which is defined as "templum". It was a special place where the Roman augurs asked for Iuppiter's approval. Nissen, starting from an analysis of the literature of Roman land surveyors, goes on to discuss temples, military camps, and towns. As we have previously shown (Sparavigna, 2020-2024), in the *Das Templum* we find the Roman town considered as a templum, an inaugurated space then, with its main axis, the decumanus, oriented towards the sunrise. The day on which the decumanus' direction was established, according to Nissen, was also the Dies Natalis of the town, associated with a festival in the Roman calendar. Let us remember that decumani and cardines were the lines used by surveyors to subdivide the land to be assigned to Roman colonists (centuriation). Nissen established his "rule" regarding the decumanus in analogy with his thought about the foundation of the temples. The long axis of a temple was determined, according to Nissen, by the sunrise on the day of its foundation. Every year this day was celebrated as the Dies Natalis of the temple. If we know the direction of the long axis, comparing it with the sunrise azimuth we can determine the festival and therefore the name of the divinity to whom the temple was dedicated. However, this is not true. The Dies Natalis was the day of the temple's dedication, which was the last act regarding its building, corresponding to its opening for public worship. The Dies Natalis was not the day when the plan of the temple was established on the ground. A further problem, evidenced in a 1869 review of Nissen's *Das Templum* by Giulio De Petra, was regarding the fact that the calendar for Greeks and Romans (before the Julian calendar) was a luni-solar calendar, and therefore the sunrise direction had nothing to do with the festivals. A further problem is the transfer from Greek temples to Roman towns of the idea that the direction of the decumanus was ruled by the sunrise (Martin Erdmann, 1883).

Here in the following Nissen's words about the Geburtstag (Dies Natalis). "Diese Erklärung, welche sich aus den Worten der Gromatiker mit Notwendigkeit ergibt, eröffnet eine ganz neue Betrachtungsweise. Wie jeder Mensch, so hat auch der Gott und die Götterwohnung und das Templum in seinen verschiedenen Anwendungen

überhaupt einen Geburtstag. Dies gilt ebenso von der Stadt: einige Geburtsjahre italischer Städte sind S. 56 zusammengestellt. So wenig wir hiervon wissen, erscheint unsere Kunde bezüglich der Geburtstage doch noch weit dürftiger. Für Rom wird er bezeichnet durch das Parilienfest am 21. April, für die Colonie Brundisium durch das Fest der Salus auf dem Quirinal am 5. August. Nach dem oben Gesagten muss also die Richtung des Decumanus entsprechen dem Sonnenaufgang am Gründungstag des Templum. Und um die Theorie auf gegebene Fälle anzuwenden, lässt sich aus dem Decumanus der Gründungstag finden, oder falls der Tag bekannt, die Richtung des Decumanus".

Imagined by Nissen as a templum with the decumanus oriented towards the sunrise on the day of its foundation, the town has a Geburtstag, a birthday, a Dies Natalis, a day which is associated with a festival (for instance, in the case of Brundisium, August 5, festival of the Salus at Quirinal). Therefore, the German historian Heinrich Nissen was the first to have associated decumanus, sunrise and festivals of the Roman calendar. No antecedents of this theory can be found in the available literature (to the best of my knowledge). An obvious problem exists: which was the day, in the long legal and religious sequence that characterized the process of founding a colony, that the colonists celebrated as Dies Natalis? This problem was discussed by Eckstein and Conventi, among many other scholars. Nobody else, in the literature about the Dies Natalis, considered it being the day when the groma, the roman surveying instrument, was posed under auspices (*posita auspicaliter*) to start the land surveying. Conventi, for instance, considers the Dies Natalis as the day when the map of the colony, the *Forma Urbis*, accompanied by the *Lex* of the colony, was placed in the Forum of the town. This was the last action regarding the foundation of the colony. Eckstein is considering the Dies Natalis as the day when the pomerium, the boundary separating the town (*urbs*) from its countryside, was ritually ploughed. Of course, this is true only in the case that an *urbs* was not present. However, we have the deduction of colonies also in lands where a town already existed.

As detailed in Sparavigna, 2020-2024, Nissen seems to have been the first to associate decumanus, sunrise, and festivals of the Roman calendar together. Nissen's *Das Templum* was used by Friedrich Nietzsche for his *Der Gottesdienst der Griechen*, which contains the lectures on the Greek cult that Nietzsche held between 1875 and 1878. Nietzsche endorsed Nissen's thesis regarding the decumanus. A totally different position is that of Isaac Valeton who, in his *De Templis Romanis* (1983), shows that the town is not a templum and therefore does not require its decumanus ritually oriented to the sunrise. Valeton demonstrated that, according to Roman laws, the ground of the town is profane, and used by common people, subjected to the rule of the magistrate, not of *augurs*. So Valeton criticizes Nissen's theory. Let us also stress the discussion by Pierangelo Catalano, 1978, regarding the spatial aspects of the Roman juridical-religious system, where Catalano reiterated that the town is not a templum. In the "Aspetti spaziali del sistema giuridico-religioso romano. *Mundus, templum, urbs, ager, Latium, Italia*", a detailed illustration of the roman "templum" in the section "Concetti di templum: *templum in caelo e templum in terris; locus designatus in aëre e templum inauguratum*" is available. We proposed and discussed elsewhere the Catalano's work, and we strongly suggest it as highly relevant for any investigation about templum and *augural science*. Other scholar studies exist, for example, those by F. Castagnoli and J. Le Gall, which say the same: the town is not a templum. Regarding the centuriation, i.e. the subdivision of agrarian land, Castagnoli, Catalano and Le Gall stress that it is not a templum. Several scholars have therefore stressed that the town is not a templum, and the same for centuriation; this fact needs to be reiterated because archaeoastronomical approaches exist proposing hypotheses about the Roman world without considering Nissen, Nietzsche, Valeton, Catalano, Castagnoli, Le Gall and others' opinions about the *templa*.

Besides what we obtained previously about Nissen's doctrine of the templum, here we consider how his work about sunrise, decumanus, templum, and the fixed boundaries of the land, passed into the Ernst Cassirer's work. But before, let us stress that, in Nissen, there is not a proper presentation of the boundaries of a town. Nissen thinks that a town was separated from another town, because of the limits established by the centuriation of their related agrarian lands. But it was not so: the town is separated by its boundary, the pomerium, from its agrarian land. This is evidencing another problem of Nissen's work, and this was stressed by De Petra, that Nissen used ancient literature just mentioning those passages which agreed with his theory. And the pomerium, which is fundamental to distinguish the town from its agrarian land, does not fit the Nissen's belief.

Returning to Cassirer, it is in his *Philosophy of Symbolic Forms*, 1925, that we can find mentioned some considerations that Heinrich Nissen proposed in his *Das Templum*, 1986. Cassirer is referring to Nissen in the section entitled “Space and Light. The Problem of Orientation”. Cassirer “believed that all the forms of representation that human beings use - language, myth, art, religion, history, science - are symbolic, and the concept of symbolic forms was the basis of his thinking on these subjects” ([Yale University Books](#)). Let us note that in Cassirer’s work on symbolic forms, the perspective proposed by Nissen is given as if it were the true Roman positions about religion and laws. It was not so, as demonstrated by Thulin, Valetton, Castagnoli and Catalano.

Michael Friedman, 2023, in *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* explains that “Cassirer’s earliest works on the philosophy of symbolic forms appeared as studies and lectures of Warburg Library in the years 1922–1925, and the three-volume *Philosophy of Symbolic Forms* itself appeared ... in 1923, 1925, and 1929 respectively”. “The philosophy of symbolic forms is oriented towards the much more general “fact of culture” and thus takes the history of human culture as a whole as its ultimate given datum. The conception of human beings as most fundamentally “symbolic animals,” interposing systems of signs or systems of expression between themselves and the world, then becomes the guiding philosophical motif for elucidating the corresponding conditions of possibility for the “fact of culture” in all of its richness and diversity” (Friedman). “Characteristic of the philosophy of symbolic forms is a concern for the more “primitive” forms of world-presentation underlying the “higher” and more sophisticated cultural forms – a concern for the ordinary perceptual awareness of the world expressed primarily in natural language, and, above all, for the mythical view of the world lying at the most primitive level of all” (Friedman, 2023). For Cassirer then, the human being is ruled by primitive manifestations of “symbolic meaning”.

The Philosophy of Symbolic Forms, Philosophie der symbolischen Formen (1923–29), is presented in three parts: *Language, Erster Teil: Die Sprache* (1923), *Mythical Thought, Zweiter Teil: Das mythische Denken* (1925), *The Phenomenology of Knowledge, Dritter Teil: Phänomenologie der Erkenntnis* (1929). Let us consider the second part, regarding the mythical thought, and the section devoted to “Space and Light. The Problem of Orientation”. It is evident from the title of this section, that we must face with Nissen's belief. Before this section, Cassirer discussed of the myth. Then, he starts mentioning the concept of space.

The space

"The intuition of space is a basic factor in mythical thinking, since this thinking is dominated by a tendency to transform all the distinctions which it postulates and apprehends into spatial distinctions and to actualize them in this form. ... we have assumed the divisions and separations of spatial direction, of right and left, above and below, etc. to be affected in the primary sense impression without the need of a special intellectual effort, a specific “energy” of consciousness. But precisely this assumption now requires a correction, for on closer scrutiny, ... It consists rather in ascertaining the fundamental motive by which mythical thinking is guided in its original setting up of these same spatial distinctions. How, in mythical space as a whole, do particular “regions” and directions come to be singled out - how does it come about that one region and direction is opposed to the others, “stressed” over against them, and endowed with a particular distinguishing mark?” (Cassirer).

“That this is no idle question becomes evident once we consider that in this differentiation mythical thinking proceeds according to entirely different criteria from those employed by theoretical-scientific thinking in mastering the same task. The latter establishes a determinate spatial order by relating the sensuous diversity of impressions to a system of purely logical, purely ideal, forms. The empirical straight line, the empirical circle, and the empirical sphere are determined and understood in reference to the ideal world of purely geometrical figures, in reference to the straight line “as such,” the circle “as such,” and the sphere “as such.” An aggregate of geometrical relations and laws is set up which supplies the norm for all apprehension and interpretation of empirical things in space. The theoretical view of physical space shows itself to be governed by the same intellectual motive” (Cassirer).

Cassirer notes that sensory intuition seems to play a part; it is evident that our physical body feels gravity. Abstracting from "the "anthropomorphic" ingredients of the physical world view", "the sensuous antithesis of "above" and "below" loses its significance in the cosmic space of physics. "Above" and "below" are no longer absolute opposites. They have validity only in relation to the empirical phenomenon of gravity and the empirical regularity of this phenomenon. Physical space is in general characterized as a space relevant to forces: but in its purely mathematical formulation the concept of force goes back to the concept of law, hence of the function. In the structural space of myth, however, we see an entirely different line of thought. Here the universal is not distinguished from the particular and accidental, the constant from the variable, through the basic concept of law; here we find the one mythical value accent expressed in the opposition between the sacred and profane. Here there are no purely geometrical or purely geographical, no purely ideal or merely empirical distinctions; all thought and all sensory intuition and perception rest on an original foundation of feeling. However subtle and particularized its structure may become, mythical space as a whole remains embedded, or one might say, immersed in this feeling. In this space, specific boundaries and distinctions are thus not arrived at by progressive logical thinking through intellectual analysis and synthesis; they go back to distinctions already made on the basis of such feeling. The zones and directions in space stand out from one another because a different accent of meaning is connected with them, and they are mythically evaluated in different and opposite senses. In this appraisal a spontaneous act of the mythical consciousness is performed; but objectively considered, it is also tied to a specific and fundamental physical fact. The development of the mythical feeling of space always starts from the opposition of day and night, light and darkness. The dominant power which this antithesis exerts on the mythical consciousness can be followed down to the most highly developed religions. Some of these religions, particularly that of the Iranians, may even be designated as complete systematizations of this one opposition. But even where the antithesis does not take on this logical form, this almost dialectical sharpness, it may be recognized as one of the latent factors in the religious structure of the cosmos" (Cassirer).

Light and sunrise

Cassirer mentions the Babylonian creation legend the world arises and then the "Egyptian story of the creation [that] has also been interpreted as an imitation of the daily sunrise. The first act of creation begins with the formation of an egg which rises out of the primal water; from the egg issues Ra, the god of light, whose genesis is described in the most diverse versions, all of which however go back to the one original phenomenon - the bursting forth of light out of darkness" (Cassirer).

Cassirer goes on to Johann Gottfried von Herder: "Perhaps Herder's gift of not seeing spiritual phenomena as mere facts but of transposing himself into the creative process from which they spring is nowhere so brilliantly revealed as in this interpretation of the first chapter of Genesis. For him the narrative of the creation is nothing other than the story of the birth of the light—as experienced by the mythical spirit in the rising of every new day, the coming of every new dawn. This dawning is for mythical vision no mere process; it is a true and original creation—not a periodically recurring natural process following a determinate rule but something absolutely individual and unique. Heraclitus' saying, "The sun is new each day," is spoken in a truly mythical spirit. Here we have, as it were, the first characteristic beginning of mythical thinking; and in all its further progress the antithesis of light and darkness, day and night, proves to be a living and enduring motif. In his fine and moving book Troels Lund followed the growth of this motif from the first primitive beginnings to that universal elaboration which it underwent in astrology. "We start from the assumption," he writes, that sense of place and receptivity to impressions of light are the two most fundamental and deep-seated manifestations of the human intelligence. ... For each inhabitant of the earth, this sphere which is itself not luminous, the interchange of light and darkness, day and night, is the earliest impulse and the ultimate end of his faculty of thought. Not only our earth but ourselves, our own spiritual I, from our first blinking at the light to our highest religious and moral feelings, are born and nurtured of the sun. ... The progressive view of the difference between day and night, light and darkness, is the innermost nerve of all human cultural development. Every separation of the zones of space and hence every kind of articulation within mythical space as a whole is connected with this contrast. The characteristic mythical accent of the sacred and profane is distributed in

different ways among the separate directions and zones and lends each of them a definite mythical-religious imprint" (Cassirer).

The myth and the river

In Cassirer we find considered the "separation of the zones of space". It is time to return to Nissen's *Das Templum*, where we find a geolocated idea of separation, which dominates the Italic mind in a mythical form.

"Die Naturformen beherrschen den Geist; sie prägen ihm ihren Stempel unauslöschlich ein zu einer Zeit, wo die jungen Sinne sich begierig den umgebenden Wundern öffnen. Wechselnde Schicksale mögen die ersten Eindrücke betäuben, aber nicht verdrängen; man versetze den Sohn der Ebene ins Gebirg, so wird er doch nie vollständig der Anschauungen sich entschlagen können, welche die weiten Flächen seiner Heimat in ihm wach riefen. Die Naturanschauung des italischen Volkes ist in der Ebene entstanden. Auf dem Boden der Ebene ist der Mensch zuerst der göttlichen Verheissung, welche die Erde ihm unterthan machte, froh geworden. Er hat hier nicht mit Mächten zu kämpfen, die stärker sind als seine junge Kraft, die Sciranken, welche sich seinem Vordringen entgegenstellen, überwältigt er mit leichter Mühe; sein strebender Geist umfasst die endlose Fläche. Der Mensch drückt ihr das Zeichen der Knechtschaft auf; die Natur zeichnet sich hier nicht durch scharf ausgeprägte Formen aus, der ordnende Verstand zwingt sie in unterscheidende Linien. Die quadratische Kunstform hat sich in Aegypten und Babylon und in gleichem Sinne bei den Italikern entwickelt. Die Geometrie, wie Varro sagt (S. 10), hat den umherschweifenden und zwieträchtigen Völkern den Frieden gebracht. Freiheit und Gebundenheit sind die beiden Pole, um welche sich das Leben des Menschen wie des Volkes dreht. Wenn die Ebene ihren Bewohner zur Freiheit prädestinirt, so gewährt sie nur das eine Element, dessen er zu seiner menschlichen Entwicklung bedarf. In den Steppen und Wüsten mit ihrer ewigen Monotonie verliert er auf der Stufe elementarer Ungebundenheit, dem Thiere gleich von Ort zu Ort schweifend. Darum sind es auch nur die begrenzten Ebenen, welche die Wiege der Cultur getragen haben : die Inseln gleich von unwirthbaren Wüsten geschützten Thäler des Nil, des Euphrat und Tigris. Durch diese Gesichtspunkte wird die Bildungsepoche der italischen Nation fest localisirt. Sie kann sich nicht am Schwarzen Meer noch an der Donau vollzogen haben, und nirgend anders als in der Ebene des Po" (Nissen, *Das Templum*).

Here in the following the translation. The natural forms dominate the mind; they imprint their mark on it indelibly at a time when the young senses are eagerly opening themselves to the unimaginable wonders. Changing fates may numb the first impressions, but not repress them; if you move a son of the plain to the mountains, he will never be able to completely rid himself of the impressions that the vast expanses of his homeland evoked in him. The Italic people's view of nature originated in the plain. It was on the soil of the plain that man first became glad of the divine promise that made the land subject to him. Here he does not have to fight with forces that are stronger than his young strength; he easily overcomes the vines that oppose his advance; his striving spirit embraces the endless expanse. Man imposes upon it the mark of servitude; Nature here is not characterized by sharply defined forms; the organizing mind forces it into distinctive lines. The square art form [in the sense of geometry, land surveying, centuriation] developed in Egypt and Babylon and in the same spirit among the Italics. Geometry, as Varro says (p. 10), brought peace to wandering and conflicting peoples. Freedom and constraint are the two poles around which the life of people and nation revolves. If the plain predestines its inhabitants to freedom, it only grants the fundamental element that he needs for his human development. In the steppes and deserts with their eternal monotony, he lives on the level of elementary freedom, wandering from place to place like an animal. That is why it is only the limited plains that have borne the cradle of culture: the islands like valleys of the Nile, Euphrates and Tigris protected by inhospitable deserts. Through these points of view the educational epoch of the Italic nation is firmly identified. It cannot have taken place on the Black Sea or on the Danube, and nowhere else than in the Plain of the Po River.

In fact, Nissen in the *Das Templum* is proposing the Po River as the decumanus of the huge plain, which is imagined as a templum. The same we can find in Nietzsche. The decumanus (Po) moves from west to east. The cardines were the Po's tributaries (north and south directions).

Four directions

Let us continue reading Cassirer. "East, west, north, and south are not essentially similar zones which serve for orientation within the world of empirical perception; each of them has a specific reality and significance of its own, an inherent mythical life. The directions are taken not as abstract and ideal relations but rather as independent entities, each endowed with a life of its own - as can be seen, for example, from the fact that they often experience the highest concrete formation and embodiment of which myth is capable, i.e. they are raised to the level of gods. Even at relatively low levels of mythical thinking we encounter these gods of direction: gods of the east and north, of the west and south, of the lower and upper world. And perhaps there is no cosmology, however primitive, in which the contrast of the four main directions does not in some way emerge as the cardinal point of its understanding and explanation of the world. Thus Goethe's saying, "God's is the orient, God's is the Occident; north and south rest in the peace of His hands," - applies in the strictest sense to mythical thinking. But before it could arrive at this unity, this universal feeling of space and of God in which all particular distinctions seem dissolved, mythical thinking had to pass through these same distinctions and set them off against one another. Each particular spatial determination thus obtains a definite divine or demonic, friendly or hostile, holy or unholy "character." The east as the origin of light is also the source of life - the west as the place of the setting sun is filled with all the terrors of death. Wherever we find the idea of a realm of the dead, spatially separate and distinguished from the realm of the living, it is situated in the west of the world. And this opposition of day and night, light and darkness, birth and death, is also reflected in countless ways in the mythical interpretation of concrete events of life. They all take on a different cast, according to the relation in which they stand to the phenomenon of the rising or setting sun. "The worship of light," writes Usener in his *Gotternamen*, is woven into the whole of human existence. Its basic features are common to all the members of the Indo-European family of peoples; indeed they extend much farther; even today, often unconsciously, we are dominated by it. ... As early as the Homeric epics the light represents salvation. ... Euripides calls the light of the day "pure." The cloudless blue sky with its unobstructed light is the divine prototype of purity and became the basis for the conceptions of the land of the gods and the sojourn of the blessed. ... And this intuition was directly transposed into the supreme moral concepts of truth and justice. ... From this fundamental view it followed that sacred actions for which the gods of heaven could be invoked as helpers or witnesses could be performed only under the open daytime sky. ... The oath, whose sanctity is based on the invocation of the all-seeing, all-knowing, punishing gods as witnesses, could originally be taken only under the open sky. The Germanic assembly in which the community of free men who dwelt in houses were united for counsel and judgment took place "in the sacred ring," under the open sky. ... All these are simple, involuntary notions; they arise under the irresistible power of sense impressions to which we have not yet grown impervious, and which form a closed circle of their own. In them springs up an original and inexhaustible well of religiosity and morality" (Cassirer).

Of course, what Cassirer is writing needs to be checked carefully. For instance, about the direction faced by worshippers, what can we tell about roman world? Catalano is telling us that *templa* (inaugurated *templa*) had several orientations. "I *templa* inaugurata avevano varie orientazioni. Un criterio generale è tramandato, da Vitruvio, non per tutti i *templa* bensì per quelli in cui fosse stata consacrata un'aedes (Vitruvio, *De arch.* 4, 5: *Regiones autem quas debent spedare aedes sacrae deorum immortalium, sic erunt constituendae uti si nulla ratio inpedierit liberaque fuerit potestas, aedis signumque quod erit in cella conlocatum spectet ad vespertinam caeli regionem, uti qui adierint ad aram immolantes aut sacrificia facientes spectent ad partem caeli orientis ad simulacrum quod erit in aede, et ita vota suscipientes contueantur aedem et orientem caelum ipsaque simulacra videantur exorientia contueri supplicantes et sacrificiantes. Sin autem loci natura interpellaverit, tunc convertendae sunt earum regionum constitutiones, uti quam plurima pars moenium e templis deorum conspiciatur. Item si secundum flumina aedes sacrae fient, ita uti Aegyptio circa Nilum, ad fluminis ripas videntur spedare debere. Similiter si circum vias publicas erunt aedificia deorum, ita constituentur uti praetereuntes possint respicere et in conspectu salutationes facere, d'altra parte, secondo Igino, il criterio generale sarebbe mutato (Igino, *De limitibus constituendis*, in Gromatici ed. LACHMANN, 169s. [. ..] non omnis agrorum mensura in orientem potius quam in occidentem spectat, in orientem sicut aedes sacrae. Nam*

antiqui architecti in occidentem templa recte spectare scripserunt: postea placuit omnem religionem eo convertere, ex qua parte caeli terra inluminatur). Di fatto si osserva che in Roma l'orientamento dell'edificio è di solito legato al tracciato urbano; tra i pochi casi di orientamento astronomico sono i templi del largo Argentina, che hanno la fronte volta ad oriente" (Catalano).

Let us stress that "aedes" is different from "templum". In a translation of Vitruvius, uchicago.edu, we can find "aedes" rendered "temples" (I report the translation using aedes instead of temple, when necessary). Catalano is mentioning aedes in inaugurated spaces. "If there be nothing to prevent it, and the use of the edifice allow it, the aedes of the immortal gods should have such an aspect, that the statue in the cell may have its face towards the west, so that those who enter to sacrifice, or to make offerings, may have their faces to the east as well as to the statue in the aedes. Thus suppliants, and those performing their vows, seem to have the eades, the east, and the deity, as it were, looking on them at the same moment. Hence all altars of the gods should be placed towards the east. But if the nature of the place does not permit this, the temple is to be turned as much as possible, so that the greater part of the city may be seen from it. Moreover, if temples be built on the banks of a river, as those in Egypt on the Nile, they should face the river. So, also, if temples of the gods be erected on the roadside, they should be placed in such a manner that those passing by may look towards them, and make their obeisance (Vitruvius).

The fact that aedes and templa are different things is stressed by Marquardt, 1886, [archive](#): "Macht dagegen der Ritus des Gotteshauses (aedes) eine Inauguration nicht nöthig, so genügt zur Weihe desselben die Consecration. Durch dieselbe wird es ein fanum, ist aber einmal für die Sitzungen des Senates unbrauchbar und zweitens an die architektonische Form des templum nicht gebunden. In diese Kategorie gehört die aedes Vestae, ein Rundbau, in dem der Senat sich nicht versammeln konnte, die aedes Herculis Victoris an der ara maxima, eine aedes ...". If the rite of the houses of gods does not require an inauguration, consecration is enough. This makes it a fanum, but firstly it is unusable for the meetings of the senate and secondly it is not bound to the architectural form of the templum. This category includes the aedes Vestae, a circular building in which the senate could not assemble, the aedes Herculis Victoris at the ara maxima, an aedes

Castagnoli, 1984, in his "Il Tempio Romano: Questioni di Terminologia e di Tipologia" notes that for the terminology relating to buildings and places of worship in ancient Rome, the research carried out by Heinrich Jordan remains essentially valid. AEADES indicates the place where the divinity dwells, while the TEMPLUM is a space defined by a ritual "augurii aut auspicii causa" (Varro). But since the aedes are also generally constituted with such a ritual, they are also temples. Therefore, the same templar building can be called either templum or aedes. In some cases, however, there are preferences. Jordan notes that Augustus in RES GESTAE uses TEMPLUM in only two cases (for Apollo Palatine and for Mars Ultor) compared to 18 cases for AEADES. The term templum generally refers to a large area bordered by porticoes and aedes a temple building enclosed in it.

Nissen's roman sacral order

Then Cassirer arrives to roman world and Nissen's belief about it.

"In all these transitions we are again immediately aware of that dynamic which belongs to the essence of every true spiritual form of expression. In every such form the rigid limit between "inside" and "outside," the "subjective" and the "objective," does not subsist as such but begins, as it were, to grow fluid. The inward and outward do not stand side by side, each as a separate province; each, rather, is reflected in the other, and only in this reciprocal reflection does each disclose its own meaning. Thus in the spatial form which mythical thinking devises the whole mythical life form is imprinted and can, in a certain sense, be read from it. This relationship found its classical expression in the Roman sacral order. In a basic work Nissen has elucidated this reciprocal transposition from all sides and shown how the mythical-religious feeling of the sacred found its first objectivization by turning outward, by representing itself in the intuition of spatial relations. Hallowing begins when a specific zone is detached from space as a whole, when it is distinguished from other zones and one might say religiously hedged around. This concept of a religious hallowing manifested concurrently as a

spatial delimitation has found its linguistic deposit in the word *templum*. For *templum* (Greek *temenos*) goes back to the root *tem*, “to cut” and thus signifies that which is cut out, delimited. It first designates the sacred precinct belonging to the god and consecrated to the god and then, by extension, every marked-off piece of land, every bounded field or orchard, whether it belongs to a god, king, or hero. But by a primal and basic religious intuition the heavens as a whole appear as just such an enclosed, consecrated zone; as a temple inhabited by one divine being and governed by one divine will” (Cassirer).

Let us stress that the “*templum inauguratum*”, that is a space where an inauguration has been made by an *àugur*, is different from a consecrated space. So let us stress once more that the reading of Catalano’s work is essential. It is not true that “by extension, every marked-off piece of land, every bounded field or orchard, whether it belongs to a god, king, or hero” is a *templum*. The town is not a *templum*, as demonstrated by Valetton.

Returning to Cassirer. “Then a sacral ordering of this unity sets in. The whole of heaven breaks down into four parts, determined by the zones of the cosmos: a hither part in the south, a nether part in the north, a left part in the east, and a right part in the west. From this first purely local partitioning developed the entire system of Roman theology. In searching the sky for omens of man’s undertakings on earth the *àugur* began by dividing it into definite sectors. The east-west line, established by the course of the sun, was bisected by a vertical from north to south. With this intersection of the two lines the *decumanus* and the *cardo*, as they were called in the language of the priests, religious thinking created its first basic schema of coordinates. Nissen has shown in detail how this schema was transferred from religious life to every sector of juridical, social, and political life, and how in this transference it became more and more precisely and subtly differentiated. It formed the basis for the development of the concept of property and the symbolism by which property was designated and safeguarded as such. For the fundamental act of “limitation,” through which fixed property was first established in the juridical-religious sense, is everywhere related to the sacral order of space. In the books of the Roman *agrimensores* limitation was attributed to Jupiter and related directly to the act of creation - as though the strict limitation prevailing in the universe had thus been transferred to the earth and to all earthly relations. Limitation is also based on the world zones, on the division of the cosmos designated by the lines from east to west and north to south, the *decumanus* and the *cardo*. It begins with the simplest natural division into a diurnal and nocturnal aspect, followed by a second division into morning and evening, the waxing and waning day. Roman political law is closely bound up with this form of limitation; upon it is based the distinction between *ager publicus* and *ager divisus et adsignatus*, between public and private property. For only land enclosed in fixed boundaries, in immutable mathematical lines, passes as private property. Like the god before them, the state, the community, and the individual now acquired a definite space through the intermediary of the idea of the *templum*, and in this space they made themselves at home” (Cassirer).

"Die Limitation [limitation, centuriation] geht aus von den Weltgegenden: eine Linie von Ost nach West und eine zweite, welche jene rechtwinklig schneidet, von Süd nach Nord bilden die Basis del ganzen Systems" (Nissen, *Das Templum*).

“It is not a matter of indifference how the *àugur* limits the sky; for although the will of Jupiter extends over the whole of it, just as the *paterfamilias* governs the whole household, other gods dwell nevertheless in the various regions, and the lines are drawn according as one interprets the will of this one or that one. Once the lines are drawn the space thus hedged about is immediately occupied by a spirit. ... Not only the city but also the *compitum* and house, not only the land as a whole but every field and vineyard, not only the house as a whole but every room within it, has its own god. The godhead is recognized by its workings and surroundings. Consequently every spirit which is confined within a given space gains an individuality, and a specific name by which man can invoke him” (Cassirer mentioning Nissen, *Das Templum*, and *Orientation. Studien zur Geschichte der Religion*).

Here it is necessary for us to note that “The word *compitum* itself furnishes information about the location. It is derived from *competo*, “come together”, “meet”, and is explained by ancient authors and modern scholars alike as “crossroads” or “a shrine at crossroads”. The few *compita* found in Rome are on streets or squares” (Bakker, 2023). What we have previously read from Cassirer, was also proposed by Nietzsche.

Here Nietzsche as translated by Posani Löwenstein. "La costituzione di un tempio ha quale diretta conseguenza l'appropriazione di uno spazio delimitato da parte di uno spirito. Non solo la città, ma anche il compitum (crocevia) e la casa, non solo il terreno coltivabile, ma anche ciascun campo e ciascun vigneto, non solo la casa considerata come un tutto, ma ogni spazio al suo interno possiede il suo dio. Ogni dio racchiuso in uno spazio ha una sua identità e un suo nome, attraverso il quale può essere invocato da un uomo. Se si riconduce la divisione spaziale al tempo, allora otteniamo gli dèi degli indigitamenta". The establishment of a temple has as its direct consequence the appropriation of a delimited space by a spirit. Not only the city, but also the compitum (crossroads) and the house, not only the arable land, but also each field and each vineyard, not only the house considered as a whole, but every space within it has its god. Each god enclosed in a space has its own identity and its own name, through which it can be invoked by a human being. If we trace the division of space back to time, then we get the gods of the indigitamenta.

"Indigitamenta" was the name given by the Romans to the set of sacred formulas with which the divinities were invoked. It was of the utmost importance that a pre-established divinity should be invoked, case by case, by its proper name and epithets, and by the proper formula. Any error made in formulating the invocation rendered its effect null and void. Hence the necessity of a thorough knowledge of the art of indigitamenta: they were under the supervision of the college of pontiffs, whose leader (the pontifex maximus) dictated, for religious acts performed on behalf of the state, the formulas to the magistrate or priest who performed them (Giulio Giannelli).

Let us return to Cassirer.

"This system - which also dominated the structure of the Italic cities, the grouping and order within the Roman camp, and the ground plan and inner arrangement of the Roman house - makes it clear how progressive spatial limitation, like every new boundary established in space by mythical thinking and mythical-religious feeling, became an ethical and cultural boundary. This relationship can be followed down to the very beginnings of theoretical science. The beginnings of Roman scientific mathematics, as Moritz Cantor has shown in a monograph, went back to the books of the Roman agrimensores and their system of spatial orientation" (Cassirer mentioning Cantor).

"Throughout the classical mathematical demonstrations of the Greeks we also discern an echo of primordial mythical notions; we feel the breath of that awe which surrounded the spatial "limit" from the very beginning. The form of logical-mathematical definition developed through the idea of spatial limitation. In the Pythagoreans and Plato limit and the unlimited, peras and apeiron, are set off against each other as the determinant and the indeterminate, form and formlessness, good and evil. Thus the purely intellectual orientation of the cosmos grew from this spatial orientation of the mythical beginnings. Language has in many instances preserved the traces of this connection; for example, the Latin term for pure theoretical thought and vision, *contemplari*, goes back to the idea of the *templum*, the marked-off space in which the augur carried on his observation of the heavens. And from the ancient world this same theoretical and religious orientation entered into Christianity and the system of medieval Christian theology (Cassirer mentioning Franz Boll's *Vita contemplativa*).

Orientazione e divisione (Catalano)

First, let us remember that, usually, the term "templum" is related to the *temenos*, from the verb "to cut". Varro is considering "templum" from "tueri", to observe. Contemplation of a templum. But, what templum? In caelo? The locus designatus in aëre? The templum inauguratum?

"La divisione del *templum in caelo* ci è così riportata da Varrone: *Eius templi partes quattuor dicuntur, sinistra ab oriente, dextra ab occasu, antica ad meridiem, postica ad septemtrionem* (Varrone, *De ling. Lat.* 7, 7). Tale divisione del tempio celeste non trova completa corrispondenza nella divisione del locus designatus in aëre, quando il soggetto che consulta Iuppiter sia orientato verso oriente (v. ad es., Livio 1, 18, 7; Isidoro, *Orig.* 15, 4, 7 *locus designatus ad orientem a contemplatione templum dicebatur. Cuius partes quattuor erant: antica ad*

ortum, postica ad occasum, sinistra ad septentrionem, dextra ad meridiem spectans); mentre la corrispondenza è completa quando il soggetto sia orientato a mezzogiorno {ad meridiem spectans Cicerone, De div. 1, 17, 31 e tal.) (Catalano). “I tempia inaugurata avevano varie orientazioni. Un criterio generale è tramandato, da Vitruvio, non per tutti i templa bensì per quelli in cui fosse stata consacrata un'aedes ... Circa l'orientazione dei luoghi limitati secondo decumanus e cardo, in generale, vedi VALETON, 1893, 410ss.; BRUGI, Le dottrine giuridiche degli agrimensori romani. Verona 1897, 232ss. 98) (Catalano).

Churches

“The ground plan and structure of the medieval Church show the characteristic features of the old mythical symbolism of the cardinal points. Sun and light are no longer the godhead itself, but they still serve as the most immediate emblems of the divine, of the divine will to salvation and power of salvation. The historical effectiveness and historical triumph of Christianity were indeed closely bound up with its ability to assimilate and refashion the basic conceptions of the pagan cults of the sun and the light. The cult of sol invictus was now replaced by faith in Christ as the “sun of righteousness.”” (Cassirer, and references therein).

“Accordingly, the early Christians retained the eastward orientation of their church and altar, while the south became the symbol of the Holy Ghost and the north conversely of estrangement from God, faith, and the light. Before baptism the novice was turned toward the west to renounce the devil and his works, and then toward the east, toward paradise, that he might profess faith in Christ. The four ends of the Cross were also identified with the four celestial and cosmic directions. And upon this simple plan was constructed the increasingly subtle and profound symbolism in which the whole of man’s inner faith turned outward as it were, objectifying itself in elementary spatial relations” (Cassirer, references therein).

“If we look back over all these examples, we cannot fail to recognize that although they belong to the most diverse cultures and stages in the development of mythical-religious thinking, they reveal the same basic characteristics of the mythical consciousness of space. This consciousness is comparable to a fine ether which pervades the most diverse manifestations of the mythical spirit and binds them to one another. Cushing writes that thanks to the sevenfold organization of their space the whole world view of the Zunis and their whole life and activity are completely systematized, so that, for example, when they occupy a new campsite the position of the different groups and clans is determined in advance. To this the structure and order of the Roman camp presents a perfect analogy, for the plan of the camp was drawn up according to that of the city, while the city in turn was constructed according to the general plan of the world and the different spatial zones of the cosmos. Polybius tells us that when the Roman army entered the site selected for their camp, it was as though citizens, returning to their native city, each sought out his own house. In both cases the local ordering of the different groups was not looked upon as something merely outward and accidental but was required and predetermined by definite sacral notions” (and Cassirer is mentioning Nissen).

Once more, the roman camp was not a templum, the town was not a templum, the centuriation was not a templum. Please, consider Le Gall and [What the Latin Literature Truly Tells Us About the Orientation of Camps, Towns and Centuriation](#).

Terminus and Time

“Everywhere such sacral conceptions are bound up with the general view of space and distinct spatial boundaries. A primordial mythical-religious feeling is linked with the fact of the spatial “threshold.” Men’s veneration of the threshold and awe of its sanctity are expressed almost everywhere in similar usages. Even among the Romans Terminus was a special god, and at the festival of the Terminalia the boundary stone itself was crowned with a garland and sprinkled with the blood of a sacrificial beast. From the veneration of the temple threshold, which spatially separates the house of the god from the profane world, the fundamental juridical-religious concept of property seems to have developed along similar lines in totally different cultural spheres. Just as it originally protected the house of the god, the sanctity of the threshold (in the form of land

markings) safeguarded house and fields against hostile trespass and attack. Often the terms coined by language for the expression of religious awe and veneration go back to a basic sensuous-spatial idea, the idea of shrinking back from a particular spatial zone. And this spatial symbolism is transferred to the intuition and expression of circumstances of life bearing only the most indirect relation, if any, to space. Wherever mythical thinking and mythical feeling endow a content with particular value, wherever they distinguish it from others and lend it a special significance, this qualitative distinction tends to be represented in the image of spatial separation. Every mythically significant content, every circumstance of life that is raised out of the sphere of the indifferent and commonplace, forms its own ring of existence, a walled-in zone separated from its surroundings by fixed limits, and only in this separation does it achieve an individual religious form. All movements into and out of this ring are governed by very definite sacral regulations. Transition from one mythical-religious sphere to another involves rites of passage which must be carefully observed. These rites govern moves from one city to another, from one country to another, and changes from one phase of life to another—childhood to puberty, celibacy to marriage, childlessness to motherhood, etc.” (Cassirer).

Cassirer continues with the myth and the time.

“We have seen that the simplest spatial relations, such as left and right and forward and backward, are differentiated by a line drawn from east to west, following the course of the sun, and bisected by a perpendicular running from north to south—and all intuition of temporal intervals goes back to these intersecting lines. Among the peoples who developed this system to the greatest clarity and perfection this relation is often echoed in the most common linguistic term for time. The Latin *tempus*, to which corresponds the Greek *temenos* and *tempos* (preserved in the plural, *tempea*), grew out of the idea and designation of the *templum*” (Cassirer).

“The basic words *temenos* (*tempus*), *templum* signified nothing other than bisection, intersection: according to the terminology of later carpenters two crossing rafters or beams still constituted a *templum*; thence the signification of the space thus divided was a natural development; in *tempus* the quarter of the heavens (e.g. the east) passed into the time of day (e.g. morning) and thence into time in general” (Cassirer reporting Hermann Usener in his famous *Götternamen*).

From [Wiktionary](#): “Two roots have been proposed: (1) from Proto-Indo-European **tempos* (“stretch”), from the extension **temp-* of the root **ten-* (“to stretch, string”), with meaning development "what is stretched, stretching" → "stretch (of time)" → "time, occasion"; (2) from Proto-Indo-European **temh₁-* (“to cut”), thus "a section (of time)", this root also giving Latin *temnō*, *tondeō*, Ancient Greek *τέμνω* (*témnō*); compare the etymology of English *time*. *Templum* is a possible cognate that has also been assigned to both roots.”

“The division of space into directions and zones runs parallel to the division of time into phases; both represent merely different factors in that gradual illumination of the spirit which starts from the intuition of the fundamental physical phenomenon of light. And by virtue of this relationship a particular mythical-religious “character,” a special accent of “holiness,” is given to time as a whole and to every phase of time in particular. As we have seen, mythical feeling looks on position and direction in space not as the expression of a mere relation but as a particular being, a god or demon, and the same is true of time and its subdivisions. Even highly developed religions have preserved this basic intuition and this belief. In the Persian religion the cult of time and the segments of time, of the centuries, the years, the four seasons, the twelve months, and particular days and hours, developed from the general worship of light. Particularly in the development of Mithraism this cult achieved great importance” (Cassirer and references therein).

“In general, the mythical intuition of time, like that of space, is altogether qualitative and concrete, and not quantitative and abstract. For myth there is no time “as such,” no perpetual duration and no regular recurrence or succession; there are only configurations of particular content which in turn reveal a certain temporal gestalt, a coming and going, a rhythmical being and becoming. Thus, time as a whole is divided by certain boundaries akin to musical bars. But at first its “beats” are not measured or counted but immediately felt. Above all, man’s religious activities show a rhythmic articulation of this sort. Specific sacral acts are meticulously assigned to definite times and seasons, outside of which they would lose all sacral power. All religious activity is organized according to very definite time intervals, e.g. periods of seven or nine days, weeks, or months. The “holy days,”

the times of festival, interrupt the uniform flow of life and introduce distinct lines of demarcation. The phases of the moon play a particular role in determining “critical dates.” According to Caesar, Ariovistus postponed hostilities until the new moon; the Lacedaemonians waited until the full moon before taking the field. The intuition underlying all this is that temporal, like spatial, intervals and dividing lines are not mere conventional distinctions of thought but possess an inherent quality and particularly, an essence and efficacy of their own” (Cassirer).

Discussion

We have seen that Cassirer has borrowed heavily from Heinrich Nissen, as far as orientation and the concept of templum are concerned. So did Nietzsche. We must ask ourselves whether what Nissen said is right or not. Nissen was wrong. The town is not a templum. The military camp is not a templum. The fields divided to be distributed to the Roman settlers are not templa. The Dies Natalis of Roman towns is not linked to the sunrise on the day that the direction of its decumanus is determined.

The town is not a templum. The soil of the town is profane. Valeton proves it in his *De Templis Romanis* (1893). In Valeton's work all the reasons are clearly expressed. Consequently, it makes no sense to think that the town should have been oriented with a ritual like that used for the templum. I. M. J. Valeton was a professor at the University of Amsterdam; he writes his discussion in Latin. Valeton writes, regarding the town's soil and decumani and cardini: “Sed ipsum urbis solum, quamvis viae quae in eo ducebantur essent vel esse deberent limites secundum rationem Decumani et Cardinis constituti, minime erat inauguratum; viae constituebantur non ab augure, sed a magistratu conditore urbis; viae erant profanae et poterant prout usus ferebat a publico consilio sine auspiciis mutari aut loco moveri. Solum urbis neque dicebatur neque erat templum; primum absurdum hoc erat, in templo nova templa inaugurari, cum tamen multa templa in urbe essent condita; deinde solum urbis ab auguribus liberatum servari non poterat, neque poterat habere religionem templorum, cum esset traditum communi et vulgari usui multitudinis urbanae”. In English: But the ground of the town, although the streets that we can find inside are, or should be, determined as limits established according to a layout based on Decumani and Cardines, the soil has not been inaugurated for sure. The streets were not established by the àugur, but by the magistrate, who was the founder of the town. The streets were profane, and could be modified or moved, depending on uses and needs, without the auspices of a public council. The ground of the town was neither called nor was it a templum. First, it would be absurd for new temples to be inaugurated in a templum, since many temples were going to be founded in the town. The land of the city could neither be kept free by the àugurs, nor could it be subjected to the religion of the temples, since it was devoted to common use and the urban population made common use of it.

About the templum and àugurs a detailed discussion is given by Pierangelo Catalano, in his 1978, regarding the spatial aspects of the Roman juridical religious system. In Catalano we find reiterated that the town is not a templum. Other scholar studies will be mentioned such as, for example, those by F. Castagnoli and J. Le Gall, which say the same. Regarding the centuriation, i.e. the subdivision of agrarian land, Castagnoli, Catalano and Le Gall stress that it is not a templum.

Once more, let us consider Catalano. “Dalle simiglianze e differenze tra templum in caelo, locus designatus in aëre, templum inauguratum possiamo ricavare: a) “ciò che è inaugurato è posto in comunicazione, in una simmetria efficace con il cielo, con le regiones caeli ove gli auguri trovano i mezzi della loro azione ; ciò che non è inaugurato resta essenzialmente terrestre” [Catalano mentioning G. DUMÉZIL, *Rituels indo-européens à Rome*]; b) la tecnica della limitazione secondo il decumanus e il cardo non è caratteristica né originaria degli àugures [note 107 in Catalano]”. From the similarities and differences between templum in caelo, locus designatus in aëre, templum inauguratum we can deduce: a) what is inaugurated is placed in communication, in an effective symmetry with heaven, with the regiones caeli where the àugures find the means of their action; what is not inaugurated remains essentially terrestrial [Catalano mentioning G. DUMÉZIL, *Rituels indo-européens à Rome*]; b) the technique of limitation according to the decumanus and the cardo is neither characteristic nor original to the àugures [note 107 in Catalano].

The note 107 in Catalano: “Vedi VALETON, locc. cit. n. 102; WEINSTOCK, *Templum* (cit. η. 99) 119ss. Mette conto ricordare che secondo Varrone l'origine della limitazione degli agri si trova nella disciplina Etrusca, cioè nell'arte degli aruspici; da questi deriva l'arte degli agrimensori (vedi Frontino, in *Gromatici*, ed. LACHMANN, 27SS.; cfr. Igino, *De limitibus constituendis*, *ibid.*, 166; Dolabella, *ibid.*, 303). Del tutto affrettata è, quindi, l'asserzione di M. TORELLI, *Un 'templum augurale' d'età repubblicana a Bantia*, *Atti Accad. Naz. Lincei*, serie VIII, *Rendiconti Classe di Scienze morali, storiche e filologiche* 21 (1966) 297, secondo cui “procedimenti di suddivisione urbanistica ed agrimensura e procedimenti di auspicio derivano dallo stesso fondo giuridico-sacrale e adoperavano metodi analoghi”. Si noti che l'orientazione per la limitatio, secondo la disciplina Etrusca, era quella ad occidente. Per un confronto con l'orientazione a mezzogiorno, usata da Atto Navio nel famoso augurium nella vigna, vedi A. SZABÓ, *Roma quadrata*, *Maia* 8 (1956) 260ss.; circa l'influsso etrusco in questo procedimento di augurium stativum, vedi P. CATALANO, *Diritto augurale* (cit. η. 2) 307 ss. Sulla permanente distinzione tra arte augurale romana e aruspicina vedi P. CATALANO, *Aruspici*, in: *Novissimo Digesto Italiano* 1 (Torino 1968) e *supra*, I, 2, p. 455. Va ripetuta qui, per l'implicito riferimento al templum aereo, la precisa domanda di Cicerone, *De div.*, 2, 35, 75: *Quid enim scire Etrusci haruspices aut de tabernaculo rede capto aut de pomerii iure potuerunt?*”

See VALETON, WEINSTOCK, *Templum*. It is worth remembering that, according to Varro, the origin of the limitation of the agrarian land is found in the Etruscan discipline, that is, in the art of haruspices; from them, it derives the art of the land surveyors (see Frontinus, in *Gromatici*, ed. LACHMANN, 27ff.; cf. Hyginus, *De limitibus constituendis*, *ibid.*, 166; Dolabella, *ibid.*, 303). It is exhibiting a lack of careful thought the assertion by M. TORELLI, *Un 'templum augurale' d'età repubblicana a Bantia*, according to whom “procedures of urban subdivision and land surveying and the procedures of auspicia derive from the same juridical-sacral base and used similar methods”. It should be noted that the orientation by limitatio, according to the Etruscan discipline, was to the west. For a comparison with the orientation to the south, used by Attus Navius in the famous augurium in the vineyard, see A. SZABÓ, *Roma quadrata*. On the Etruscan influence in this process of augurium stativum, see P. CATALANO, *Diritto augurale*. On the permanent distinction between Roman augural art and haruspicin, see P. CATALANO, *Aruspici*. It is necessary to repeat here, for the implicit reference to the aerial templum, the precise question of Cicero, *De div.*, 2, 35, 75: *Quid enim scire Etrusci haruspices aut de tabernaculo rede capto aut de pomerii iure potuerunt?*

And also from Catalano: “È necessario sottolineare come dalle fonti non risulti che l'Etruscus ritus esigesse, per l'inaugurazione del pomerium, una limitazione secondo il decumanus e il cardo (pur restando questa, ovviamente, possibile); né che esigesse una certa orientazione. In ciò si ha concordanza tra le fonti scritte ed i dati archeologici.” Catalano stresses the persistent error “fra gli studiosi di antichità, nonostante i risultati già raggiunti dal Valeton, 1892, 387 n.1; 1893, 63s.; 425; 1895, 64ss.; cfr. 1893, 62—91 (par. 3: 'De ratione decumani et cardinis diversa a ratione templorum terrestrium et aliena a reliquis templis); 397—440; 1895, 15—24 (par. 4: 'De religione limitationis)’”. It is necessary to emphasize that the written sources do not show that the Etruscus ritus required, for the inauguration of the pomerium, a limitation according to the decumanus and the cardo (although this remains, of course, possible); nor that it required a certain orientation. In fact, there is agreement between the written sources and the archaeological data. Against this persistent error which is relating the pomerium to the decumanus, see Valeton. Valeton tells also ... cum ratio Decumani et cardinis prorsus aliena sit ab omnibus significationibus vocabuli templum (que sunt templum aerium et templum caeleste), una (templi terrestris) excepta, non licet hanc rationem designare nomine templi.

About the templum, Cassirer and Nietzsche followed the Nissen's doctrine. Since Nissen's doctrine was suitable to Cassirer's opinion about the forms, Cassirer accepted it as true. But Nissen was not right about the templum. And Cassirer has not questioned Nissen's doctrine. However, it is evident that Nissen's *Das Templum* has been criticized in the past with well-founded criticisms. It was criticized even in the reviews that have been published as soon as the Nissen's book started its circulation.

In Pelgrom, 2018, we can find that “the survey archaeology suggests a trajectory of rural settlement change in Italy which was unrelated to Roman expansion”, and this “requires us to reanalyze the evidence of land division lines” (that is, limitation, centuriation). “More than the phenomenon of rural settlement intensification, these lines are believed to express the values of private property, civic order, rationalism and technological progress,

which are so fundamental to socio-evolutionary models of the late nineteenth century”, and as a reference Pelgrom is mentioning the *Das Templum* of Nissen. However, the “view which holds Rome responsible for the creation of such rigidly divided landscapes in Italy continues to be reproduced”. Pelgrom stresses that “this accepted view is not based on solid evidence, but is strongly determined by aprioristic assumptions derived from socio-evolutionary paradigms”. In fact, this is what we find in the Ernst Cassirer approach to Nissen’s doctrine, an aprioristic assumption that Nissen’s paradigm about the templum were true. But it is not so.

Archeoastronomy

At the beginning of our discussion, we mentioned that Clive Ruggles considers Nissen as an archaeoastronomer. Archaeoastronomy, which seems to have as its main aim that of finding possible alignments with sun, moon and stars, almost ignored for the roman world the works by Nissen, Nietzsche, Valetton, Thulin, Catalano, and also Cassirer. The fact that the town is not a templum concerns Roman Laws and Religion, and thus it is also affecting any related archaeoastronomical guess.

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